
26-27 MARCH 2025

i3S - INSTITUTO DE
INVESTIGAÇÃO E
INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE
UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO

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INSTITUTO
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12TH GALENUS
INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP:

Bioengineering the future of drug delivery

GALENUS
FOUNDATION
Vienna • Austria

WELCOME MESSAGE

Dear colleagues,

We are excited and truly honored to welcome all of you to the **12th Galenus International Workshop: Bioengineering the future of drug delivery** in Porto, Portugal, at i3S - Institute for Research and Innovation in Health, March 26-27, 2025. This is a unique event organized in collaboration with the Galenus Foundation.

Join us for an innovative workshop aimed at pushing the boundaries of knowledge and encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration. We will bring together emerging and leading experts working at the interface of drug delivery science, bioengineering, designer biomaterials and pharmaceutical technology. By combining these diverse research fields, we hope to create a dynamic environment that fosters interdisciplinary scientific exchange and enhances the overall value of our research efforts.

A diversity of topics will include nanomedicine, pharmaceutical formulations for the delivery of bioactives, tissue engineering, gene delivery and editing, and many more. Get inspired by a line-up of renowned and outstanding invited speakers from academia and industry.

In addition, young scientists (early career researchers) will have the chance to present their interdisciplinary research in dedicated sessions. By providing a platform for young scientists to present their work, we aim to showcase their scientific advancements and contribute to foster future collaborations. Abstract oral presentations were selected by our Scientific Committee based on criteria such as novelty, significance, clarity and impact. Moreover, the Young Scientist Poster Networking Session will provide a valuable opportunity for discussion, networking and knowledge exchange with senior scientists and potential collaborators. Awards will be given to the best oral and poster presentations.

We wish you enjoy this unparalleled opportunity to engage with leading experts, connect to your (young scientist) peers, and shape the future of bioengineering and drug delivery.

“Bem-vindos ao Porto!” – Welcome to Porto!

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Bioengineering the future of drug delivery

The Influence of Starches from Various Botanical Sources on the Rheological and Adsorptive Properties of Galenic Stiff Zinc Oxide Paste

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Zinc oxide (ZnO) paste is a commonly used Galenic formulation, typically composed of 25% zinc oxide, 25% talc, and 50% petrolatum. However, talc use has been under scrutiny due to its potential contamination with asbestos and quartz, both class 1 carcinogens [1]. Given the need for safer and more sustainable excipients, this study aimed to investigate the effects of starches from various botanical sources and their particle size on the rheological properties and adsorption capacities of stiff ZnO paste.

Eight formulations of 25% ZnO paste were compounded according to the *Magistral Formulae 2008* of the Republic of Serbia [2], incorporating tapioca, rice, maize starch, or talc in two particle sizes (140 μm or 355 μm). Rheological properties were assessed using amplitude and frequency sweep tests. Water adsorption capacity (WAC) and oil adsorption capacity (OAC) were also evaluated [3].

Amplitude sweep tests showed that the G' values (elastic modulus) were higher than G'' (viscous modulus) in all formulations, indicating their predominant solid-like nature. The highest G' and G'' values were observed in tapioca starch-based pastes, which were the most impacted by the particle size. The lowest G' and G'' values were found in ZnO paste with talc. Frequency sweep tests revealed that the pastes were resistant to structural changes under stress, with G' prevailing over G'' at all frequencies. Tapioca starch exhibited the best WAC, while the talc-based formulation had the highest OAC. A reduction in particle size improved both WAC and OAC (Figure 1). Starch granule size, structure, amylose/amylopectin ratio and molecular weight majorly impact its functional properties [4].

The results of this study demonstrate that replacing talc with starches alters the rheological and adsorptive properties of Galenic ZnO paste, with tapioca starch having the most pronounced effect, potentially enhancing its sensory profile, patient acceptance, and therapeutic effectiveness.

Figure 1. Water and oil adsorption capacity (%) of stiff ZnO pastes expressed per gram of sample; T-tapioca starch; R-rice starch, M-maize starch, TL-talc.

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